

Thatcherism's greatest achievement

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Abstract:

Through two powerful quotes, we learn how deeply former Conservative Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher influenced New Labour: she claimed Tony Blair was her greatest achievement, and Blair later acknowledged that he kept many of her reforms and even sought her advice. Together, the quotes reveal how Thatcher reshaped Britain's political landscape and entrenched neoliberalism in the UK and beyond.

Keywords: Margaret Thatcher, Tony Blair, New Labour, neoliberalism, institutional change

In 2002, twelve years after Margaret Thatcher left office, she was asked at a dinner what was her greatest achievement. Thatcher replied: “**Tony Blair and New Labour. We forced our opponents to change their minds.**” ([Conor Burns, April 11, 2008](#))

As Tony Blair himself told: “[Thatcher] was immensely kind and generous to me when I was Prime Minister... Politically, certain reforms she made, for example in Trade Union Law..., we kept the basic legal framework... We didn't renationalise many of state industries that she privatized... **I always thought my job was to build on some of the things she had done rather than reverse them...** Many of the things she said... had a certain creditability... Whenever I wanted to ask her for advice, she would always give it... in a genuine, spirited way.” ([BBC News, April 8, 2013](#))

These excellent books elaborate on this matter:

- *The Political Economy of New Labour: Labouring under False Pretences?* by Colin Hay (Manchester University Press, 1999)
- *New Labour and Thatcherism: Political Change in Britain*, by Richard Heffernan (Palgrave Macmillan, 2000)
- *New Labour, New Language?* by Norman Fairclough (Palgrave Macmillan, 2000)
- *Transforming Local Governance: From Thatcherism to New Labour*, by Gerry Stoker (Palgrave, 2003)
- *A Brief History of Neoliberalism*, by David Harvey (Oxford University Press, 2005)
- *Thatcher And Sons: A Revolution In Three Acts*, by Simon Jenkins (Penguin, 2007)
- *The Thatcherite Offensive: A Neo-Poulantzian Analysis*, by Alexander Gallas (Brill, 2015)